

ISMS Scope Statement

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Revision History

Version	Date	Created By	Description of Changes
1.0	03/15/2026	Stefan Krauss (ISM)	Initial release of ISMS Scope Statement

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1. Purpose

This document establishes the scope of the Information Security Management System (ISMS) for CasePilot LLC. It clarifies the boundaries, applicability, and overall coverage of the ISMS across the organization.

2. Scope Statement

The Information Security Management System (ISMS) applies to CasePilot LLC as a legal entity, including all operations, functions, and activities carried out under the direction and oversight of the Executive Leadership.

3. Scope Justification

The defined scope of the ISMS is aligned with CasePilot LLC's governance structure, operational model, and risk environment.

CasePilot operates as a single, self-contained legal entity with its own executive management, functional departments, defined processes, and independent IT environment. As such, it represents an organizational unit capable of independently establishing, operating, and continually improving an Information Security Management System (ISMS).

Given that CasePilot is a cloud-based SaaS provider that processes sensitive legal, personal, and financial information, information security is integral to all organizational functions and service delivery activities.

The scope therefore includes all organizational units, personnel, physical locations, and information systems that create, process, store, or transmit information relevant to its operations.

The selected scope ensures that information security risks are addressed comprehensively and that the ISMS is implemented at a level of governance capable of enforcing policies, allocating resources, and maintaining accountability across the organization.

4. Organizational Boundaries

4.1. Legal Entity

The ISMS applies to the legal entity CasePilot LLC. There are no subsidiaries, parent companies, or affiliated entities within the defined scope.

4.2. Organizational Units

The ISMS applies to all organizational units of CasePilot LLC across the organization:

- Executive Leadership
- Product & Engineering
- Infrastructure & DevOps
- Sales & Marketing
- Customer Success & Support
- Finance & Revenue Operations
- Compliance & ISMS
- People Operations (HR)

All personnel, regardless of department or work arrangement are included within the scope of the ISMS

4.3. Processes

The ISMS covers all core and supporting processes necessary for the delivery and operation of CasePilot LLC's SaaS services:

- Strategic planning and corporate governance
- Product development and software engineering
- Cloud infrastructure and IT operations
- Sales and marketing activities
- Customer onboarding and implementation
- Customer support and success services
- Billing, payments, and revenue operations
- Compliance, legal, and risk management
- Human resources and people operations
- Finance and administrative functions

4.4. Services

The ISMS applies to all products and services developed, operated, and supported by the organization.

It includes the delivery and operation of CasePilot Pay™, CasePilot Practice™, and CasePilot Immigration™, as well as all supporting activities required to design, develop, host, maintain, secure, and support these cloud-based solutions.

5. Physical Boundaries

The ISMS applies to the following physical environments:

- The headquarters of CasePilot LLC located in Austin, Texas, United States.
- Remote and hybrid work locations used by authorized personnel when accessing or processing company and client information.

6. Information System Boundaries

The ISMS applies to all information systems that store, process, or transmit CasePilot or client information. The boundaries of the information systems are defined as follows:

6.1. Networks

Corporate and cloud-based networks used to operate CasePilot services, including:

- Internal office networks
- Remote access connections
- Cloud-based virtual networks within AWS
- Wireless network used at the headquarters

6.2. Operating Systems

Operating systems supporting business and production activities, including:

- Windows and macOS endpoints used by personnel
- Linux-based production and application servers hosted in AWS
- Mobile device operating systems used for authorized business purposes

6.3. Applications and AI Systems

Applications and AI-enabled systems used to develop, deliver, and support CasePilot services, including:

- CasePilot Pay™, CasePilot Practice™, and CasePilot Immigration™
- AI-powered customer support chatbot functionalities
- AI-assisted development and code generation tools
- Development and CI/CD tools
- Source code repositories
- CRM systems

- Billing and financial management systems
- HR and payroll systems
- Security monitoring and logging tools

6.4. Databases and Information Repositories

Structured and unstructured data stores containing:

- Client legal matter data
- Personally identifiable information (PII)
- Financial and payment transaction records
- Employee records
- System logs, audit trails, and backup repositories

6.5. Business and Technical Processes

Processes that create, access, modify, transmit, or store information, including:

- Software development and release management
- Customer onboarding and support
- Billing and payment processing
- Risk management and compliance activities
- Human resources and administrative operations

6.6. Telecommunications and Security Equipment

Equipment and technical controls supporting connectivity and protection, including:

- Firewalls and secure gateways
- Routers and switching equipment
- Identity and access management systems
- Endpoint protection and monitoring solutions

6.7. Hardware Assets

Physical computing and endpoint devices used to access, process, store, or transmit CasePilot or client information, including:

- Corporate-issued laptops and workstations
- Mobile devices authorized for business use
- Office networking equipment
- Security appliances
- Backup devices and storage media

7. Exclusion

The following exclusion applies to the ISMS scope:

- a) The physical security controls and operations of Amazon Web Services (AWS) data center facilities. These facilities are owned, managed, and operated by AWS and fall under the AWS Shared Responsibility Model.

CasePilot LLC remains responsible for the secure configuration, logical security, access management, data protection, and monitoring of all cloud resources deployed within AWS environments. This exclusion does not affect the organization's responsibility for protecting information assets hosted in the cloud.